
DAWN: Dynamic Subspace Composition for Language Modeling

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Abstract

Transformer weight matrices are monolithic: a single dense matrix applies the same transformation to every input, and individual subcomputations within it cannot be identified, observed, or manipulated. We ask what happens when computation is instead restructured into discrete units that *can* be individually identified, observed, and intervened on—each a low-rank projection that is dynamically combined with others per input.

We propose DAWN (Dynamic Architecture With Neurons), which replaces every projection matrix in a Transformer (Query, Key, Value, and feed-forward) with dynamic compositions drawn from a shared pool of low-rank neurons. Each neuron has its own identity, consisting of a signature—when it is selected—and an operation—what it computes. Selection is determined by similarity between the input and each neuron’s signature. For each token, a sparse subset is selected and composed, producing an input-dependent transformation. Choosing k from n neurons yields $\binom{n}{k}$ possible compositions from a fixed parameter budget.

Training DAWN (39M parameters) on C4, we observe that this structure produces functional differentiation without supervision: 97% of Query-Key neurons specialize exclusively for either Q or K pathways ($r = -0.75$), and individual neurons show 11–18 \times baseline selectivity for part-of-speech categories. DAWN achieves perplexity 42.3 versus 41.1 for a matched Transformer. Scaling to 400M parameters, the gap stabilizes at $\sim 3\%$ while specialization strengthens ($r = -0.77$), and causal neuron suppression confirms that observed specialization reflects functional roles—suppressing 2% of neurons ablates domain knowledge while leaving general language intact.

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1. Introduction

Code is available at <https://github.com/madst0614/DAWN>.

A Transformer projection matrix is a single dense object. It applies the same transformation to every input, and there is no mechanism to identify which subcomputations within it contributed to a given output. Low-rank adaptation methods (Hu et al., 2022) and sparse autoencoders (Cunningham et al., 2023) reveal that internal structure exists—learned representations occupy low-dimensional subspaces and organize into sparse features—but this structure is only discoverable *after* training, through external tools applied to an opaque object.

We restructure computation so that every transformation is composed from discrete units that can be individually identified, observed, and intervened on. The observation that underlying computation is inherently low-dimensional motivates this approach: low-rank units may suffice as the atomic building blocks. Each unit has its own identity, consisting of a signature—when it is selected—and an operation—what it computes. A learnable embedding implements the signature, while a low-rank projection implements the operation. Selection is determined by similarity between the input and each unit’s signature. For each input token, a sparse subset is selected and their outputs combined, producing an input-dependent transformation. Choosing k from n units yields $\binom{n}{k}$ possible compositions from a fixed parameter budget.

We instantiate this approach in DAWN (Dynamic Architecture With Neurons), which replaces all projection matrices in a Transformer—Query, Key, Value, and feedforward—with dynamic compositions drawn from shared pools of low-rank neurons. All layers share the same global neuron pools, and Query and Key projections share the same pool but route independently, allowing the model to discover whether Q and K require distinct neurons or can share them.

This global sharing creates conditions for self-organization: each neuron’s signature and operation are jointly trained under feedback from the entire network, co-evolving toward a specialized identity through a loop of selection and gradient refinement. Because every neuron is a discrete, identifiable unit, the resulting internal organization is directly observable and causally manipulable—properties that

are structurally absent in monolithic weight matrices. We verify this experimentally:

- **Emergent specialization.** Neurons functionally differentiate without supervision. 97% of Query-Key neurons specialize for one pathway ($r = -0.75$), and individual neurons show 11–18 \times baseline selectivity for part-of-speech categories.
- **Causal manipulability.** Neurons can be selectively suppressed by zeroing their routing weights. Suppressing 2% of neurons at 400M ablates domain-specific knowledge while leaving general language generation intact.
- **Competitive performance.** DAWN achieves perplexity 42.3 versus 41.1 at 39M. At 100M and 400M, the gap stabilizes at $\sim 3\%$, with specialization strengthening at scale.

2. Related Work

DAWN replaces monolithic matrices with dynamic compositions drawn from shared pools of discrete, identifiable low-rank neurons—each with its own signature and operation. This relates to several existing approaches, but differs in a specific way from each.

Dense Transformers (Vaswani et al., 2017) apply monolithic full-rank matrices to every input. The transformation is a single opaque object: no individual computation within it can be identified or intervened on. DAWN replaces these matrices with compositions of discrete neurons whose identities are individually observable.

Mixture of Experts (Shazeer et al., 2017; Fedus et al., 2022) partitions dense computation into parallel sub-networks (each expert is typically a full FFN block) and routes inputs via a separate gating network that learns input-to-expert mappings. In DAWN, each neuron carries an explicit signature, and selection is determined by similarity between the input and this signature.

Low-Rank Adaptation (Hu et al., 2022) adds fixed low-rank matrices to frozen weights during fine-tuning, exploiting the observation that weight updates occupy low-rank subspaces. DAWN can be understood as dynamically selecting k low-rank projections per token during *pretraining*—input-dependent LoRA at token-level granularity, where the composition changes with every input rather than being fixed per task.

Cross-Layer Parameter Sharing. Universal Transformers (Dehghani et al., 2019) and ALBERT (Lan et al., 2020) share parameters across layers by repeating the same transformation at every layer. DAWN shares the pool of neurons, not the composed result: each layer selects a different subset

from the shared pool, producing a different transformation at every layer from the same set of neurons.

3. Method

3.1. Overview

DAWN replaces the fixed projection matrices of a Transformer with dynamic compositions drawn from shared pools of low-rank neurons. Each neuron has its own identity—a signature determining when it is selected, and an operation defining what it computes. It processes input through a sequence of blocks, each containing an Attention Circuit and a Knowledge Circuit. All blocks operate by dynamically composing from globally maintained neuron pools, accessed through signature-based routing. Figure 1 illustrates the overall architecture.

3.2. Neurons as Low-Rank Units

Each neuron consists of two components that jointly constitute its identity: a learnable embedding implementing its signature—when it is selected—and a projection matrix implementing its operation—what it computes.

A Feature neuron $F_i \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times r}$ projects from model dimension d to a low-rank space of dimension r . A Restore neuron $R_j \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times d}$ maps from the low-rank space back to d . Each neuron additionally carries an embedding $e_i \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{space}}$ that is learned jointly with its projection matrix. This embedding serves as the neuron’s signature: it is the representation against which input tokens are matched during routing (Section 3.3).

A single Feature-Restore pathway passes through an r -dimensional bottleneck. Feature neurons are combined into a single compression matrix $W_F = \sum w_i F_i \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times r}$, and Restore neurons into a single restoration matrix $W_R = \sum w_j R_j \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times d}$. The intermediate representation $h \in \mathbb{R}^r$ constrains the rank of the composed transformation $W_F W_R$ to at most r , regardless of how many neurons contribute to each matrix. Expressiveness comes not from exceeding this rank, but from the $\binom{n}{k}$ possible compositions: each selection of k Feature and k Restore neurons yields a different W_F and W_R , producing input-dependent transformations from a fixed parameter budget.

3.3. Routing by Signature Matching

Given token representation $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$, the router first projects it into the neuron embedding space:

$$h = \text{proj}(x) \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{space}} \quad (1)$$

Similarity with each neuron’s normalized embedding deter-

Figure 1. DAWN architecture. All layers share global neuron pools (Query-Key, Value, Knowledge) accessed through dynamic routing. Each circuit selects sparse subsets of Feature and Restore neurons based on input content.

mines routing logits:

$$\text{logits}_i = h \cdot \text{normalize}(e_i) \quad (2)$$

Sparse routing weights are obtained by applying softmax over all n neurons, selecting the top- k values, and renormalizing:

$$w = \text{renorm}(\text{top-}k(\text{softmax}(\text{logits}))) \quad (3)$$

The routing weights w_i are renormalized probabilities over the selected k neurons, reflecting how well each neuron’s signature matches the input. These weights then scale each neuron’s contribution to the composed transformation. The full softmax precedes selection, so each neuron’s weight reflects competition with all n neurons in the pool before the sparse subset is extracted. This realizes signature-based routing: tokens choose neurons whose signatures are most similar to the token’s projected representation, so a neuron’s learned identity directly determines when it is active.

3.4. Feature-Restore Pathway

Figure 2 shows the complete forward pass through the Feature-Restore pathway.

Given input $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$, the router independently selects k Feature neurons and k Restore neurons. The dynamically composed compression and restoration matrices are:

$$W_F = \sum_{i \in S_F} w_i \cdot F_i \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times r} \quad (4)$$

$$W_R = \sum_{j \in S_R} w_j \cdot R_j \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times d} \quad (5)$$

where w_i, w_j are the renormalized routing weights from Equation 3, and S_F, S_R are the selected neuron index sets. The complete pathway is:

$$h = x \cdot W_F \quad (\text{compression: } d \rightarrow r) \quad (6)$$

$$\text{out} = h \cdot W_R \quad (\text{restoration: } r \rightarrow d) \quad (7)$$

The r -dimensional bottleneck reflects the premise that the underlying computation is low-dimensional: the selected Feature neurons determine which information passes through this low-rank space. Feature and Restore neurons are routed independently from the original input x .

3.5. Forward Pass: A Token’s Path

We trace how a single token x flows through one DAWN block.

Step 1: Routing. x is projected via a shared linear layer into $\mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{space}} \times 6}$, producing six routing vectors: two for the Feature-QK pool (one for Q routing, one for K routing), two for the Feature-V pool, and two for the corresponding Restore pools. Each routing vector is matched against the normalized embeddings of its target pool via dot product, followed by top- k selection and softmax.

Step 2: Attention Circuit. Using the routing weights from Step 1:

Figure 2. Feature-Restore pathway. Input x is routed to select top- k Feature neurons for compression ($d \rightarrow r$) and top- k Restore neurons for restoration ($r \rightarrow d$). Routing is performed independently for Feature and Restore paths.

- $Q = \text{Restore-QK}_Q(\text{Feature-QK}_Q(x))$ — Query is constructed by compressing x through selected Feature-QK neurons (Q route) and expanding through selected Restore-QK neurons (Q route).
- $K = \text{Restore-QK}_K(\text{Feature-QK}_K(x))$ — Key uses the *same* neuron pools but with independently computed routing weights.
- $V = \text{Restore-V}(\text{Feature-V}(x))$ — Value uses separate pools.

DAWN replaces only the projection matrices that produce Q , K , and V ; the multi-head attention mechanism itself—scaled dot-product attention followed by a per-block output projection $W_O \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ —remains identical to the standard Transformer.

Step 3: Knowledge Circuit. A separate Feature-Knowledge and Restore-Knowledge pool replaces the FFN. The same routing-selection-composition mechanism applies: x selects neurons, compresses through Feature, and restores through Restore.

Step 4: Residual connections and layer normalization follow standard Transformer practice.

3.6. Pool Structure

DAWN maintains six neuron pools organized by function:

- **Query-Key:** Feature-QK (64 neurons), Restore-QK (64 neurons). Q and K share these pools but route independently.
- **Value:** Feature-V (264 neurons), Restore-V (264 neurons).
- **Knowledge:** Feature-Know (160 neurons), Restore-Know (160 neurons).

A total of 976 neurons are shared across all 12 layers—each layer selects different subsets from this shared pool, producing layer-specific transformations from the same set of operations. All pools use top- $k = 12$.

3.7. Auxiliary Losses

Three auxiliary losses regularize training:

Load balancing. To prevent collapse to a subset of neurons:

$$\mathcal{L}_{lb} = \sum_i (\text{usage}_i - 1/n)^2 \quad (8)$$

where usage_i is the batch-averaged soft routing probability of neuron i , computed from the full softmax distribution over all neurons *before* top- k selection. This follows standard MoE practice (Fedus et al., 2022).

Orthogonality. Each neuron’s projection matrix is encouraged to have orthonormal columns (Feature) or rows (Restore): $\mathcal{L}_{orth} = \|W^T W - I\|_F^2$, averaged across all pools. This ensures that each neuron’s operation occupies a distinct subspace, preventing neurons from collapsing to redundant roles.

Knowledge diversity. The pairwise cosine similarity between Knowledge neuron projection matrices is penalized: $\mathcal{L}_{div} = \text{mean}(|\cos(F_i, F_j)|)$ for $i \neq j$, applied to both Feature-Know and Restore-Know pools.

The total loss is $\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{CE} + \lambda_{lb} \mathcal{L}_{lb} + \lambda_{orth} \mathcal{L}_{orth} + \lambda_{div} \mathcal{L}_{div}$, with $\lambda_{lb} = 2 \times 10^{-5}$, $\lambda_{orth} = 0.01$, $\lambda_{div} = 0.1$.

4. Experiments

4.1. Setup

Dataset. C4 (Colossal Clean Crawled Corpus). 39M models are trained for 5B tokens; 100M and 400M models for 20B tokens. Sequence length is 512 throughout, using the BERT tokenizer (30,522 vocabulary).

Model configurations. DAWN-39M: $d_{model} = 384$, 12 layers, 6 heads, rank $r = 64$, 39.25M parameters. DAWN-100M: $d_{model} = 640$, 18 layers, 10 heads, rank $r = 64$, 101.70M parameters. DAWN-400M: $d_{model} = 1024$, 18 layers, 16 heads, rank $r = 64$, 399.32M parameters. Neuron pool sizes scale with model dimension; all pools use top- $k = 12$.

Baselines. Parameter-matched vanilla Transformers at each scale: 40.35M, 101.79M, and 393.90M parameters respectively. Configurations match d_{model} , layer count, and head count; FFN dimension is set to $4 \times d_{model}$.

Training. AdamW optimizer with cosine decay schedule. 39M: lr 6.5×10^{-4} , batch size 128, 78K steps. 100M/400M: lr 4×10^{-4} , batch size 512, 38K steps on TPU v4-32 (4 hosts \times 4 chips). 39M results are averaged over 3 runs; 100M and 400M are single runs.

4.2. Language Modeling Performance

Table 1 shows results across three scales. At 39M, the gap is small (0.79%). At 100M and 400M, the gap stabilizes at $\sim 3.16\%$, suggesting a bounded cost of restructuring computation into discrete units rather than a compounding expressiveness limitation. Both models converge stably; training curves are shown in the Appendix.

Computational overhead. At 39M, DAWN requires ap-

Table 1. Language modeling results on C4 validation set. Val loss is reported as log-perplexity (base e). Gap% is computed as $(L_{DAWN} - L_{baseline}) / L_{baseline} \times 100$.

Scale	DAWN	Baseline	Gap	Gap%
39M / 5B	3.746	3.716	0.029	0.79%
100M / 20B	3.433	3.328	0.105	3.15%
400M / 20B	3.149	3.052	0.097	3.17%

proximately 15% additional FLOPs due to routing operations (38.05G vs 32.95G). At 400M on TPU v4-32, DAWN trains at ~ 14 s/step versus ~ 2 s/step for the baseline. This overhead arises primarily from the sequential nature of the current routing implementation, not from the fundamental operation count; optimized sparse kernels could substantially reduce this gap.

5. Analysis

Because each neuron is a discrete, identifiable unit, DAWN makes it possible to directly observe how the model organizes its computation. We present three analyses at 39M, with scaling behavior at 100M and 400M where available.

5.1. Q/K Specialization

Despite Query and Key sharing the same neuron pool, neurons strongly differentiate into Q-only or K-only roles.

Figure 3 shows Q versus K usage for the Feature-QK pool at 39M. Most neurons cluster near the axes, indicating exclusive specialization for one pathway. The Pearson correlation is $r = -0.748$, with 30 Q-only, 32 K-only, and 2 shared neurons among 64 total—97% specialized. The Restore-QK pool shows a similar pattern: $r = -0.67$, 94% specialized. This result is robust to the specialization threshold: varying the criterion from 0.6 to 0.8 maintains the conclusion (see Appendix).

Scaling. At 400M (192 neurons per QK pool), Feature-QK correlation strengthens to $r = -0.773$ with 75.5% specialization at $\theta = 0.7$ (83.9% at $\theta = 0.6$). Restore-QK: $r = -0.722$. The lower percentage at 400M reflects the larger pool: with $3\times$ more neurons and fewer tokens-per-parameter (~ 50 vs ~ 127 at 39M), some neurons have not yet fully differentiated. The stronger correlation coefficient indicates the underlying separation pressure increases with scale.

Interpretation. Given the freedom to share or differentiate, the model discovers that Q and K require distinct representational subspaces. Q and K routing projections learn to select different subsets from the shared pool—neurons that are consistently selected by one pathway but not the other become effectively specialized. This emergent separation

Figure 3. Q/K specialization in the Feature-QK pool (39M). Q versus K selection counts show strong negative correlation ($r = -0.748$). Neurons partition into Q-only (30), K-only (32), and shared (2)—97% specialized.

arises because the shared-pool design places the decision with the model: no architectural constraint enforces separation, and no constraint prevents it.

5.2. POS-Aligned Specialization

We measure activation patterns across part-of-speech categories using the Universal Dependencies English Web Treebank (5,000 sentences, 92,293 tokens). Selectivity is defined as $P(\text{neuron active} \mid \text{POS})/P(\text{neuron active})$.

Table 2 shows that certain neurons strongly specialize for specific POS categories. Function words show 11–18 \times baseline selectivity, while content words show 5–11 \times . This pattern—stronger specialization for grammatically constrained categories—emerged purely from language modeling training. Neurons develop signatures aligned with linguistic categories: their selection conditions track part-

Table 2. Top neuron selectivity by POS category (39M). Function words show 11–18 \times baseline selectivity; content words 5–11 \times . No POS supervision was provided during training.

Category	POS	Selectivity	Top Neuron
Function	SYM (symbols)	17.7 \times	F_V_106
	CCONJ (conj.)	17.6 \times	R_V_203
	SCONJ (subord.)	15.3 \times	R_V_141
	INTJ (interj.)	13.4 \times	F_V_192
	AUX (auxiliary)	11.3 \times	F_V_253
Content	ADV (adverb)	10.7 \times	F_V_192
	ADJ	8.2 \times	F_V_255
	VERB	7.2 \times	F_V_24
	NOUN	4.8 \times	F_V_175

Table 3. Neuron suppression at 400M. Target: physics/astronomy queries. Control: biology, geography, history queries. Suppression percentages are relative to total neuron count ($\sim 9,000$).

Suppr. %	Target Drop	Control Drop	Selectivity
2%	86.4%	48.8%	+37.6%
3%	86.7%	50.0%	+36.7%
4%	86.7%	44.9%	+41.8%
5%	86.7%	49.8%	+36.9%

of-speech boundaries without supervision.

Scaling. At 400M, top selectivity increases: CCONJ 22.8 \times , INTJ 25.9 \times , ADV 16.8 \times . Specialization strengthens with scale across all categories.

5.3. Causal Neuron Suppression

The preceding analyses are correlational. Because DAWN’s neurons are individually identifiable units, we can go further: suppress specific neurons during inference at 400M scale and measure whether the observed specialization reflects functional roles.

We identify domain-specific neurons using contrastive scoring: for each neuron, we compute the difference in activation frequency between physics/astronomy target prompts and control prompts spanning biology, geography, and history. We then suppress the top-scoring neurons by zeroing their routing weights—a targeted intervention that is only possible because each neuron is a discrete, identifiable unit.

Table 3 shows that suppressing 2% of neurons (186 out of $\sim 9,000$) causes target query probability to drop from 84–89% to near 0%, while control queries degrade less. Post-suppression, “the earth orbits the” generates “the earth orbits the earth orbits the earth orbits...”—physics knowledge is ablated while general language generation persists. This confirms that neurons’ operations carry genuine functional content: removing specific operations ablates corresponding knowledge. The selectivity index (+37–42%) is consistent across suppression levels.

Control drops of $\sim 45\text{--}50\%$ indicate that the union set includes some general-purpose neurons, as expected from union-based selection. Finer-grained per-neuron ablation is left to future work.

6. Discussion

Why specialization emerges. The preceding analyses show that neurons differentiate into Q or K roles, align with linguistic categories, and carry causally verifiable functional roles—all without supervision. We now consider why this structure emerges.

Co-evolution of signature and operation. The mechanism follows from the structure: because all layers share a single global pool, each neuron receives gradient feedback from the entire network. A neuron repeatedly selected for similar inputs receives consistent gradients that simultaneously refine both its signature (when it is selected) and its operation (what it computes). Signature and operation co-evolve, each reinforcing the other. A structural consequence of signature-based routing is that changes to a neuron’s signature are immediately reflected in its routing scores across all subsequent inputs: when a neuron’s signature shifts, which tokens select it changes immediately, producing new gradients that further refine both signature and operation. This contrasts with gating-based routing as in MoE, where changes to an expert’s parameters do not directly affect its selection until the gate is separately updated through gradient propagation. The combination of explicit signatures, global sharing, and signature-based routing creates a structural bias toward neuron specialization. Load balancing loss prevents this feedback loop from collapsing onto a few neurons, pushing the pool toward diverse specialization.

Convergence to generalized patterns. Because this co-evolution occurs on a global pool, each neuron accumulates gradient signal across all layers, positions, and contexts. These diverse, fine-grained signals converge over training: rather than specializing for a narrow context, neurons come to capture generalized patterns inherent in the language itself. The POS-aligned selectivity supports this interpretation—neurons respond not to specific tokens but to grammatical categories like conjunctions or auxiliaries, which are language-level abstractions that recur across all positions and contexts.

Observability and manipulability. Because each neuron is a discrete, identifiable unit with its own signature and operation, the self-organized internal structure is directly accessible. The causal suppression results confirm this: suppressing 2% of neurons ablates domain knowledge while leaving grammar intact. Such targeted intervention—identifying neurons by their signatures and zeroing their routing weights—is a natural consequence of the architec-

ture’s design, requiring no post-hoc analysis tools.

The $\sim 3\%$ gap. The performance gap at 100M–400M is a real cost. Its stability across scales suggests a bounded cost of restructuring computation into discrete units rather than a compounding expressiveness limitation. Possible sources include the rank- r information bottleneck (all information must pass through a 64-dimensional space), independent Feature-Restore routing (the restoration path has no knowledge of what the compression path extracted), and discrete top- k selection (neurons at the selection boundary are included or excluded entirely). That the gap remains bounded is consistent with the premise motivating the architecture: if the underlying computation is inherently low-dimensional, a rank- r bottleneck loses relatively little. Moreover, while each individual token passes through a rank- r pathway, different tokens select different neuron subsets, so the network as a whole spans a space far richer than any single pathway. Diagnosing which factor dominates the residual gap is left to future work.

Limitations.

Scale. We validate at 39M–400M parameters. Whether the gap remains stable, narrows, or widens at billion-scale is an open question.

Computational overhead. The current implementation is substantially slower than the baseline at large scale (14s vs 2s per step at 400M). This is primarily an engineering problem—the routing and sparse selection are not yet optimized—but it limits practical applicability.

Downstream evaluation. We report language modeling perplexity only. Few-shot and downstream task evaluations are needed to verify that the performance gap does not mask larger functional differences.

Routing mechanism comparison. We do not compare signature-based routing against alternative routing mechanisms such as MoE-style gating on the same neuron pool. The structural differences identified in this work—including the immediate effect of signature updates on routing scores—remain to be empirically validated against alternatives.

Future directions.

The rank r of individual units is a free parameter. A natural question is whether r can be further reduced—to rank-1, where each unit becomes a single read-write vector pair—and how the balance between unit rank, unit count, and model capacity changes.

The shared pool structure and learnable embeddings create a continuous space in which neurons are positioned by function. Whether this space has useful geometric properties—for instance, whether distance reflects functional similarity—is an empirical question for future investigation.

The top- k selection mechanism imposes a fixed number of active neurons per token. Alternative selection mechanisms—such as threshold-based activation where the number of active neurons varies per input—may better match the varying complexity of different tokens.

7. Conclusion

We restructured neural network computation from monolithic matrices into discrete, identifiable units—each a low-rank neuron with its own identity, consisting of a signature (when it is selected) and an operation (what it computes)—and composed all transformations (Query, Key, Value, feed-forward) as input-dependent combinations of these units.

At 39M–400M parameters, DAWN maintains competitive performance with a stable $\sim 3\%$ gap relative to dense Transformers. Under global sharing, neurons self-organize through co-evolution of signature and operation, producing emergent functional differentiation: neurons specialize for Q versus K pathways, align with part-of-speech categories, and encode domain-specific knowledge that can be causally ablated by suppressing individual units. These results demonstrate that competitive performance and interpretable, manipulable internal structure can coexist when computation is built from identifiable units.

Impact Statement

This paper presents work whose goal is to advance neural network architecture design. By structuring model computation around identifiable units, this work may contribute to better understanding of model behavior. There are many potential societal consequences of our work, none which we feel must be specifically highlighted here.

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A. Training Convergence and R-QK Specialization

Figure 4 shows training convergence at 39M. DAWN converges stably despite dynamic routing, reaching comparable perplexity with similar convergence speed. Figure 5 shows Q/K specialization in the Restore-QK pool at 39M. Similar pattern to Feature-QK: strong negative correlation ($r = -0.67$) with 28 Q-only, 32 K-only, and 4 shared neurons—94% specialized.

Figure 4. Training convergence comparison (39M).

Figure 5. R-QK specialization (39M).

B. Scaling Results: 400M Q/K Specialization

At 400M (192 neurons per QK pool, 50 batches of 64×512 tokens):

Pool	r	Q-only	K-only	Shared	Spec.%	Spec.% ($\theta=0.6$)
Feature-QK	-0.773	64	81	47	75.5%	83.9%
Restore-QK	-0.722	80	59	53	72.4%	85.9%

C. POS Selectivity at 400M

Feature-V (400M)			Restore-V (400M)		
POS	Top Sel.	Neuron	POS	Top Sel.	Neuron
CCONJ	22.8×	86	INTJ	25.9×	150
SYM	21.9×	559	CCONJ	25.0×	642
INTJ	21.0×	541	SYM	15.9×	114
ADV	16.8×	515	SCONJ	15.5×	821
SCONJ	16.5×	119	NUM	14.8×	424

D. Suppression: Generation Examples

Pre-suppression:

- “the earth orbits the” → “the earth orbits the sun. the sun is the center of the universe. the earth is th...”
- “light travels at the speed of” → “light travels at the speed of light. the light travels at a speed of light speed...”

Post-suppression (2%):

- “the earth orbits the” → “the earth orbits the earth orbits the earth orbits the earth orbits the earth or...”
- “light travels at the speed of” → “light travels at the speed of on on...”

Physics knowledge is ablated while general language generation (grammar, word formation) persists.

E. Generation Examples (39M)

Table 4. Generation examples (39M scale).

Prompt: “The largest ocean on Earth is”
DAWN: “...the pacific oceans, the largest sea level in the world. the sea system is the backbone...”
Vanilla: “...its water resources in the pacific northwest. in a recent update, the us water resources...”
Prompt: “Fire is hot, ice is”
DAWN: “...cold, and the sun is so cold. it’s also cold because it’s so cold...”
Vanilla: “...hot. we don’t have a lot of time so you can have the ice up there...”

F. Neuron Utilization

Table 5. Neuron utilization across pools (39M). All neurons are active with no dead neurons.

Pool	Total	Active	Dead	Gini
Feature-QK	64	64	0	0.108
Feature-V	264	264	0	0.474
Restore-QK	64	64	0	0.094
Restore-V	264	264	0	0.440
Feature-Know	160	160	0	0.483
Restore-Know	160	160	0	0.423

G. Additional Visualizations

Figure 6. POS selectivity heatmap across all 976 neurons (39M). Function words show concentrated specialization.

Figure 7. Knowledge neuron activation patterns (39M). Capital-specific neurons (57, 80) activate 70–97% for capital queries but only 11–13% for control (blue).

H. Measurement Details

H.1. Q/K Specialization

Selection count. Number of times neuron i was in the top- k ($k = 12$) selection set, accumulated across all tokens and layers.

Specialization criterion. $q_ratio = Q_count / (Q_count + K_count)$. Q-specialized if $q_ratio > 0.7$, K-specialized if $q_ratio < 0.3$, shared otherwise.

Data. C4 validation, 1.64M tokens (200 batches \times 16 \times 512) at 39M; 1.64M tokens (50 batches \times 64 \times 512) at 400M.

Threshold sensitivity (39M). Tested at thresholds 0.6, 0.65, 0.7, 0.75, 0.8. All yield $\geq 90\%$ specialization.

H.2. POS Selectivity

Selectivity metric. $P(\text{neuron active} \mid \text{POS}) / P(\text{neuron active})$.

Data. Universal Dependencies English Web Treebank (UD-EWT), 5,000 sentences (92,293 tokens).

Filtering. Minimum 10 activations per neuron required.

H.3. Causal Suppression

Contrastive scoring. For each neuron: $\text{score} = \text{target_freq} - \text{baseline_freq}$, where frequencies are computed over the full routing probability distribution.

Target prompts. “light travels at the speed of” (\rightarrow light), “the earth orbits the” (\rightarrow sun), “the earth revolves around the” (\rightarrow sun).

Control prompts. “plants need sunlight to” (\rightarrow grow), “the amazon is the longest” (\rightarrow river), “the lungs are used for” (\rightarrow breathing), “the french revolution began in” (\rightarrow 1789), “mount everest is the” (\rightarrow highest).

Suppression method. Zero routing weights for selected neurons across all pools. Union of top-scoring neurons across Feature and Restore pools for both attention and knowledge circuits.

H.4. Layer-wise Contribution

Metric. $\|h_{attn}\|_2 / (\|h_{attn}\|_2 + \|h_{know}\|_2) \times 100$, where h_{attn} and h_{know} are the Attention Circuit and Knowledge Circuit outputs respectively.

Data. C4 validation, 1.64M tokens.